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PSYCHOLOGICAL CONTENT OF PERSONALITY RESILIENCE ПСИХОЛОГІЧНИЙ ЗМІСТ РЕЗИЛЬЄНТНОСТІ ОСОБИСТОСТІ

Представлено проблему резильєнтності у психології, яку доцільно розглядати у трьох площинах: 1) як рису чи здатність у подоланні стресу, 2) як процес копіngu та 3) як адаптаційно-захисний механізм особистості, що дозволяє чинити опір стресу чи адаптуватись після психотравми. Показано, що резильєнтність забезпечує високу адаптивність, психологічне благополуччя та успішність діяльності індивіда.

Ключові слова: *резильєнтність, стресостійкість, адаптивність, копіngи, захисні механізми.*

The problem of resilience as the ability to resist stress and demonstrate mental stability has been sufficiently developed in foreign psychology, but Ukrainian researchers have not yet adapted or developed their own means of psychodiagnosis and development of resilience.

In a broad sense, resilience is the ability to build a normal, fulfilling life in difficult conditions (Lazos, 2018), resilience is considered both a process and a property of successful adaptation to various external influences, as a means of developing resilience, the former being systemic in the structure of a person's resilience (Hryshyn, 2021).

In general, the phenomenon of resilience in psychology is understood in three ways: as a trait or ability of a person, as a process, and as an adaptation and defense mechanism of a person. In addition, resilience can be defined as 1) positive personal qualities, positive sustainable motivation and successful adaptation in difficult life circumstances; 2) resistance to destruction, effective protection under strong environmental pressure; 3) building a full-fledged socially adapted life in difficult conditions (Hryshyn, 2021) Розглянемо основні визначення резильєнтності з позицій цих трьох підходів.

Resilience as a personality trait/skill. Resilience is a complex, multidimensional and inherently dynamic set of human characteristics. Resilience is the ability of an adult who has been exposed to a single potentially devastating event (such as the death of a loved one or a life-threatening situation) to maintain relatively stable, healthy levels of psychological and physical functioning, as well as the ability to experience positive emotions and learn from their own experiences (Hryshyn, 2021).

The structure of resilience has two main components: physical resilience as an indicator of stress resistance and tolerance, and psychological resilience, which includes the development and maintenance of social contacts, the use of social support, finding meaning in difficult events or situations, improving

educational level and mastering various psychotechnologies that help develop and overcome negative consequences after stress. Resilient people have three characteristics: a strong acceptance of reality; a deep belief that life has meaning, backed by strong values; and an extraordinary ability to improvise. Resilience embodies personal qualities that allow a person to grow in the face of adversity (Hryshyn, 2021).

Resilience is the ability (potential or manifested) of a dynamic system to successfully adapt to disturbances that threaten the system's functioning, viability, or development; positive adaptation or development in the context of negative impact. Resilience is the ability to successfully overcome pressure from negative factors and demonstrate flexibility in a stressful situation (Hryshyn, 2021).

In the context of exposure to significant adversity, whether psychological, environmental, or both, resilience is an individual's ability to find a way to life-giving resources, including opportunities to experience feelings of well-being; and the condition of the individual's family, community, or cultural environment that allows them to access such resources and feelings in a way that is appropriate to that culture (Hryshyn, 2021).

The characteristics of a resilient individual include the ability to be happy and satisfied with a sense of life direction and meaning; the ability to work productively with a sense of competence and control over the environment, emotional stability; self-acceptance; self-knowledge; realistic and undistorted perception of oneself, others, and the environment; interpersonal competence, the ability to have warm and caring relationships with others, to have intimacy and mutual respect; interpersonal understanding and warmth; confident optimism, autonomous and productive activity; skillful expressiveness (Hryshyn, 2021).

Resilience can be viewed as a process. In this context, resilience comprises a set of flexible cognitive, behavioral, and emotional responses to acute or chronic adversity that may be both unusual and familiar to the individual. Resilience is the ability and dynamic process of adaptively coping with stress and adversity while maintaining normal psychological and physiological functioning. Resilience is a dynamic process that encompasses positive adaptation in the context of experiencing significant life adversity. Resilience is the process of overcoming the negative consequences of traumatic events, successfully dealing with the traumatic consequences after these events, and avoiding negative trajectories of life and development associated with risk (Hryshyn, 2021).

Resilience can be viewed as a positive adaptation/defense mechanism: Resilience is a positive adaptation in the context of significant challenges that differently address the human ability to handle them, or the outcomes of successful life development during or as a result of potentially life-changing events (Hryshyn, 2021).

Psychological resilience can be defined as an individual's ability to withstand and adapt to adverse and traumatic events. Resilience is a personal characteristic of an individual that moderates or mitigates the negative effects of

stress and promotes adaptation. Resilience is a process of adaptation of a person in conditions of exhaustion, trauma, after tragedies, threats; in the face of constant sources of stress (for example, family and relationship problems, serious health problems, constant stress at work and financial problems). Resilience is the ability of a dynamic system to successfully adapt to disturbances that threaten the functioning, viability, or development of that system. Resilience is the ability of a person to adapt in the face of tragedy, trauma, various adversities, and to constant life stressors (Hryshyn, 2021).

Resilience can be viewed as a defense mechanism that allows people to succeed in the face of adversity; developing resilience can be an important goal of therapy and prevention (Hryshyn, 2021). Resilience is a hypothesized set of protective factors that protect a person from maladjustment after a stressful exposure (Hryshyn, 2021).

Key messages that we can draw from theoretical research: most definitions of resilience are based on the two main concepts of adversity and positive adaptation, and resilience is needed to respond to a variety of adverse events, from routine daily quarrels to important life events, and positive adaptation should be conceptually appropriate to the adverse event in terms of the area of life affected and the significance of the event (Hryshyn, 2021).

Resilience is an integrated adaptation of physical, mental and spiritual aspects to a set of «good or bad» circumstances, a consistent sense of self that makes it possible to maintain normative developmental tasks at different stages of life (Hryshyn, 2021).

Resilience is a bio-psycho-social phenomenon that encompasses personal, interpersonal, and social experiences and is a natural result of various developmental processes over time (Lazos, 2018). Lazos notes that resilience is generally related to the ability of the psyche to recover from adverse conditions. Depending on the focus and subject of the study, resilience can be considered both as a certain personality characteristic inherent in a particular person and as a dynamic process that plays an important role in the ability and formation of post-traumatic stress growth of a person (Lazos, 2018).